

On Colloidal Electrolytes: An Attempt to Account for the Donnan Potential and Osmotic Pressure of Gum Arabic Acid Sols under the conditions of Donnan Membrane Equilibrium

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It has been shown from Briggs data, that the osmotic pressure, p , of arabic acid sols, under the conditions of Donnan membrane equilibrium in which the concentration of each of the diffusible electrolytes, HCl and NaCl used in the outside solution, has been kept constant can be calculated from the following equation,

$$P = RT\theta K(\text{Cl})_w [\exp(eE_f/kT) + \exp(-eE_f/kT) - 2]$$

in which E_f represents the observed Donnan potential, e , the elementary charge, $(\text{Cl})_w$ the concentration of the chloride ions in the outside solution found by Briggs, K a constant and θ , equal to $C/(K_0 + C)$, C , being the concentration of arabic acid and K_0 , a constant.

It has been also shown that under the aforesaid experimental conditions, the Donnan potential E_f varies directly as θ , since the other variables are kept constant.

Osmotic pressure under the conditions of Donnan membrane equilibrium:

ACCORDING to Donnan's theory¹ of membrane equilibrium, for a system consisting of a strong electrolyte H^+A^- and a colloidal electrolyte H_2G , where G represents the colloidal anion of valency Z and H^+ the counter ion, the following equations should hold good,

$$P = RT[(\text{H})_c + (\text{A})_c - (\text{H})_0 - (\text{A})_0] + RTG \quad \dots (1)$$

and

$$\frac{(\text{H})_c}{(\text{H})_0} = \frac{(\text{A})_0}{(\text{A})_c} = R \quad \dots (1a)$$

where P represents the osmotic pressure, $(\text{H})_c$, $(\text{A})_c$ and G , the activity of the counter ions, co-ions and the colloidal anions respectively in the colloid or inside chamber and $(\text{H})_0$ and $(\text{A})_0$ the activity of the counter ions and co-ions respectively in the outside chamber containing the aqueous solution, the two chambers being separated by a membrane permeable to the ions, H^+ and A^- only.

Besides the equations (1) and (1a), the condition for electroneutrality of the ions in each chamber must hold good.

In many cases the term involving, G , in equation (1) is very small compared to the other terms and may

be neglected. The equation (1) may then be written as,

$$P = RT[(\text{H})_c + (\text{A})_c - (\text{H})_0 - (\text{A})_0] \quad \dots (2)$$

$$= RTD \quad \dots (2a)$$

where $D = [(\text{H})_c + (\text{A})_c - (\text{H})_0 - (\text{A})_0]$

It has been shown by the author in a previous paper² that

$$P = RT[(\text{H})_c + (\text{A})_c - (\text{H})_0 - (\text{A})_0]$$

$$= RT\theta[(\text{H})_s + (\text{A})_s - (\text{H})_0 - (\text{A})_0] \quad \dots (2b)$$

$$= RT\theta D_s \quad \dots (2c)$$

where $\theta = C/(k_0 + C)$, C , representing the concentration of the colloidal ion expressed in an arbitrary unit, K_0 a constant, $(\text{H})_0$ and $(\text{A})_0$ have the same significance as stated already and $(\text{H})_s$ and $(\text{A})_s$ are proportionality constants which may be interpreted to represent the activity of the respective ions associated with a unit area of the diffuse double layer at the plane of contact with the membrane.

The Donnan potential:

The Donnan potential *i.e.*, the potential difference between the two solutions, one in the colloid chamber and the other in the outside chamber, when the diffusible ions are all univalent, may be represented by the following equation;

$$E_f = \frac{kT}{e} \ln \frac{(\text{H})_c}{(\text{H})_0} = \frac{kT}{e} \ln \frac{(\text{A})_0}{(\text{A})_c} = \frac{kT}{e} \ln R \quad \dots (3)$$

where E_f represents the Donnan potential, R the ratio of $(H)_c/(H)_0$ etc. and the other terms have their usual significance.

As pointed out by Donnan and Allmand³ it cannot be measured directly by inserting two reversible electrodes into the two chambers when the system is in equilibrium *i.e.*, when the pressure on the solution in the colloid chamber is equal to the sum of the atmospheric pressure and the (equilibrium) osmotic pressure and that on the outside solution equal to the atmospheric pressure only. If the equilibrium is disturbed by bringing the pressure on both the solutions to the level of one atmosphere, then it should be possible to determine the Donnan potential directly by inserting two suitable reversible electrodes into the two chambers*. However, the procedure usually adopted is to separate the two solutions, measure the activity of the selected ionic species in each of them and then calculate the Donnan potential from the activity data.

It has been shown by the author⁴ in a previous publication that for colloidal acids the following equation holds good;

$$(H)_c = a_s\theta + (H)_0(1-\theta) \quad \dots (3a)$$

where $(H)_c$ is the activity of the H^+ ions (*i.e.*, the counterions) at sol concentration, C , a_s , the activity of the H^+ ions associated with a unit area of the diffuse double layer at the plane of contact with the electrode and $(H)_0$ the activity of the H^+ ions in the intermicellar liquid in the colloid chamber. In another publication² it has been proved that under the condition of Donnan equilibrium $(H)_0$ is also equal to the activity of the H^+ ions in the outside chamber.

If E_c and E_0 be the E.M.F. corresponding to $(H)_c$ and $(H)_0$ then equation (3a) can also be written as

$$-E_c = -[\theta E + E_0(1-\theta)] \quad \dots (3b)$$

where E is the corresponding proportionality constant. When the sol concentration, C approaches zero, E_c approaches E_0 , since θ is zero. Again when the sol concentration, C approaches infinite, θ becomes unity and E becomes equal to E_∞ , the other variables remaining constant. Therefore, eqn. (3b) may be written as follows:—

$$-(E_c - E_0) = -(E_\infty - E_0)\theta \quad \dots (3c)$$

Now $(E_\infty - E_0)$ is constant and may be denoted by E_k and as already pointed out by Leeb⁵ and Overbeek⁶ $(E_c - E_0)$ is the Donnan potential which may be denoted by E_f . The equation (3c) may then be expressed as follows:—

$$E_f = E_k\theta \quad \dots (4)$$

The equation (4) can be subjected to experimental test under the condition in which E_k remains constant, but θ varies. This condition is fulfilled when the concentration of the diffusible electrolytes added is maintained constant, while the concentration of the colloidal electrolyte alone is varied within certain limits.

Experimental data of Briggs and the osmotic pressure equation:

In one set of experiments, Briggs⁷ has kept the concentration of each of the diffusible electrolytes, HCl and NaCl constant and varied the concentration of arabic acid only. In each case, after the system has attained equilibrium, the osmotic pressure is measured, the two solutions are then separated and the H^+ ion activity in both the solutions are determined by the potentiometric method. From the activity data, the ratio, R and the Donnan potential have been found.

The concentration of each kind of ions, $(Na)_c$, $(Na)_w$ and $(Cl)_c$, $(Cl)_w$ in the colloid and the outside chambers⁵ has been calculated from a knowledge of the total amount of each taken, the volumes V_c and V_0 of the solutions in the two chambers and the ratio, R . Briggs has further assumed that the concentrations of the ions, Na^+ and Cl^- thus found are equal to their activities.

For the system investigated by Briggs⁷, the equation (2) for osmotic pressure, in terms of the activities of the ions, involved, may be written as follows:

$$P = RT[(H)_c + (Na)_c + (Cl)_c - (H)_0 - (Na)_0 - (Cl)_0] \quad \dots (5)$$

Since

$$\frac{(H)_c}{(H)_0} = \frac{(Na)_c}{(Na)_0} = \frac{(Cl)_c}{(Cl)_0} = R, \quad \dots (5a)$$

so the equation (5) can also be expressed in terms of the Donnan potential E_f as follows:

$$P = RT\{(H)_0\{\exp(eE_f/kT) - 1\} + (Na)_0\{\exp(eE_f/kT) - 1\} + (Cl)_0\{\exp(-eE_f/kT) - 1\}\} \quad \dots (5b)$$

where e is the elementary charge and the other terms have their usual significance.

The condition for electroneutrality requires that in the outside chamber, $(H)_0 + (Na)_0 = (Cl)_0$ assuming that they have the same activity coefficient.

* Some authors think that a system consisting of a sol of a colloidal electrolyte in contact with its ultrafiltrate is in thermodynamic equilibrium. It may be pointed out that such a system is not in thermodynamic equilibrium. The colloidal particles will spread into the ultrafiltrate and when their concentration will attain the same value everywhere in the entire system, then only the state of thermodynamic equilibrium will be reached.

Therefore, equation (5b) may be further simplified and written as follows :

$$P = RT(Cl)_0[\exp(eE_f/kT) + \exp(-eE_f/kT) - 2] \dots (5c)$$

In equation (5c), $(Cl)_0$ represents the activity of the chloride ions in the solution in the outside chamber. The quantity $(Cl)_w$ which Briggs has found mainly from the concentration data is different from $(Cl)_0$ in equation (5c). †Just as in the case of D_w (excess concentration) discussed in the previous paper², so in the case of $(Cl)_w$ also it has been found that $\theta K(Cl)_w$ should be put equal to $(Cl)_0$ in equation (5c). With this substitution, equation (5c) may be written as follows :

$$P = RT\theta K(Cl)_w[\exp(eE_f/kT) + \exp(-eE_f/kT) - 2] \dots (5d)$$

where K is constant.

Equation (5d) agrees well with the experimental data of Briggs recorded in Table A of this paper.

Determination of K, K₀ in θ and E_k :

The sample of arabic acid used by Briggs⁷ is the same as described in the previous paper³, so K_0 in θ must be equal to 43.3 as stated therein. Therefore, for a selected experimental value of $(Cl)_w$ knowing P and E_f , K can be found from equation (5d). Similarly from equation (4) using an experimental value of E_f and knowing the corresponding value of θ , the value of E_k can be found easily. The value of E_k thus found is 74.4 mV.

Notes on the data recorded in Table A :

In Table A are recorded the data taken from Table 1 of Briggs paper⁷. In Table A, C represents the concentration of arabic acid in grams per 1000 grams of water, K_0 in θ is 43.3 and K equal to 1.26, RT at 25° has been taken as 25280 cm. of water, $(Cl)_w$ equal to $15.3 \times 10^{-4}N$, kT/e equal to 25.6 mV and E_k equal to 74.4 mV. Under the head, Donnan

† It is also to be noted that $(Cl)_w$ constitutes an important term in the determination of D_w by Briggs.

potential "Observed" in column 3 are recorded the value of E_f found by Briggs from measurements of H^+ ion activities of the solutions of the colloid and the outside chambers.

TABLE A

Conc. of arabic acid C	θ	Donnan potential E in mV.		Osmotic Pressure P in cm. H ₂ O	
		Observed	Calculated from eqn. (4)	Observed	Calculated from eqn. (5d)
19.94	0.315	23.9	23.4	14.5	14.3
26.67	0.381	28.7	28.3	27.3	25.8
31.90	0.424	32.6	31.6	37.8	37.8
37.93	0.467	34.7	34.7	48.7	48.6
54.82	0.559	40.3	41.6	85.7	82.8
60.13	0.581	42.6	43.2	97.4	98.3
64.69	0.599	44.2	44.6	110.5	110.9
67.74	0.610	45.3	45.4	119.5	120.1

It will be noticed from the data recorded in Table A that the values of Donnan potential calculated from equation (4) agree well with those found by Briggs. The agreement between the values of osmotic pressure observed and those calculated from equation (5d) using the observed values of E_f will also appear fairly satisfactory. It appears that to fit $(Na)_w$ and $(Cl)_w$ found by Briggs, equation (5a) should be written as

$$\frac{(H)_c}{(H)_0} = \frac{\theta K(Na)_c}{\theta K(Na)_w} = \frac{\theta K(Cl)_w}{\theta K(Cl)_c} = R$$

so that equation (5c) may assume the form;

$$P = RT\theta K(Cl)_w[\exp(eE_f/kT) + \exp(-eE_f/kT) - 2].$$

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